

Strategy to achieve Nitrification and Carbon Removal from Synthetic Refinery Wastewater in a Sequencing Batch Reactor

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Abstract

Biological nitrogen removal from sewage and various industrial wastewaters *via* nitrification and denitrification is widely reported. However, achieving nitrification in recalcitrant refinery wastewater is challenging due to inhibition and washout of nitrifiers. This study addressed the challenge of achieving nitrification and carbon removal in synthetic refinery wastewater (SWW) by acclimatisation (and granule cultivation) of the activated sludge from dairy industry in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR) under aerobic conditions with influent chemical oxygen demand (COD) of 225.8 mg/L (containing various carbon and nitrogen containing organic compounds present in refinery wastewater) and total nitrogen (TN) of 30 mg/L (ammonium-N, organic-N and nitrate-N). Two acclimatisation strategies were tested: (i) direct exposure of sludge to 100% SWW, and (ii) gradual acclimatisation approach where a simple carbon source (sodium acetate) was replaced by SWW in a stepwise manner, maintaining constant COD (225.8 mg/L). Direct exposure to 100% SWW inhibited nitrification, achieving ~60% COD removal and negligible TN removal. Gradual acclimatisation facilitated granule formation and improved SBR performance, achieving 95% COD removal and complete nitrification, with sludge volume index (SVI) < 100 mL/g. High solids retention time (SRT) of 65 days, hydraulic retention time (HRT) of 40 hours, and sludge granulation possibly promoted nitrification and achieved excellent COD removal. Presence of nitrifiers was confirmed *via* fluorescent in-situ hybridization (FISH). However, denitrification was observed to be limited, which thus affected TN removal.

Keywords

Acclimatisation, Denitrification, Nitrogen, Nitrification, Refinery wastewater

INTRODUCTION

Biological nitrogen removal from refinery wastewater is challenging due to the presence of recalcitrant compounds (such as phenols, aromatic hydrocarbons, heavy metals, and nitrogenous organics) and low biodegradable carbon. These compounds often inhibit sensitive nitrifiers, leading to their washout in full-scale treatment systems (Wu et al., 2024; Steeves, 2022) and thereby hindering nitrification, the first step in nitrogen removal. Moreover, refineries frequently report elevated ammonium-N concentrations at the outlet of biological units due to the breakdown of nitrogenous heterocyclic compounds (Kusworo et al., 2021). Consequently, simultaneous removal of mixed carbon and nitrogen sources, along with ammonium-N, remains a critical challenge in refinery wastewater treatment. To address this, novel strategies may leverage sludge from industries rich in nitrifying and denitrifying communities (such as dairy sludge) to cultivate aerobic granular sludge (AGS). AGS offers structural protection for sensitive microorganisms against inhibitory organics; however, its application in refinery wastewater remains limited. This study aimed to acclimatise and granulate dairy sludge to achieve effective nitrification and carbon removal in synthetic refinery wastewater containing organic and nitrogenous compounds. The study was conducted in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR) operated under fully aerobic conditions. While AGS cultivation has been reported at high organic loading rates (>1–2 kg COD m⁻³·day⁻¹), this work demonstrates the feasibility of developing AGS at a low organic loading rate (<0.2 kg COD m⁻³·day⁻¹) and achieving simultaneous removal of organic carbon and nitrogen compounds, along with complete nitrification, in refinery wastewater.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Source of sludge and formulation of synthetic refinery wastewater

The activated sludge used in the SBR studies was procured from the aerobic tank of a full-scale wastewater treatment plant from a dairy industry, based in Goregaon, Mumbai.

Synthetic refinery wastewater (SWW) was formulated based on characterisation of real refinery wastewater and GCxGC TOF-MS analysis (data not shown). SWW consisted of a mix of organic carbon and nitrogen containing organic compounds together with inorganic nitrogen sources (in mg/L): phenol (2), naphthalene (1), anthracene (0.5), cresol (1), hexadecane (1) and biphenyl (1), aniline (54), quinoline (32), ammonium-N (10.2) provided using ammonium chloride and nitrate-N (8.7) provided using potassium nitrate. Additional inorganic nutrients added were (mg/L): Phosphorus (2) provided using KH_2PO_4 (4.5) and K_2HPO_4 (5.7); MgSO_4 (22.5), $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (27.5), FeCl_3 (0.25); and trace metals solution (TMS: 1 mL/L). TMS included (mg/L): H_3BO_3 (0.0620), $\text{MnCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.2807), ZnCl_2 (0.1363), $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.0392), $\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.0254), $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.0382), NiCl_2 (0.0130), $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.7016) and Na_2SO_4 (0.1420). Sufficient alkalinity was added for nitrification (~7 times TKN) by dosing NaHCO_3 . Total COD of the influent SWW was: 225.8 mg/L and TN (100% SWW feed) was ~30 mg/L.

Acclimatisation and cultivation of AGS in SBR

A 7 L SBR was started up with activated sludge from a dairy industry biological treatment plant. The reactor was operated in aerobic mode with SWW, using a hydraulic retention time (HRT) of 40 h, solids retention time (SRT) of ~65 days and volume exchange ratio (VER) of 60%. Aeration was provided by air pumps to maintain dissolved oxygen at 5–6 mg/L and mixing was done at 200 rpm (using REMI stirrer). The pH ranged from 7 to 8.5. The SBR cycle lasted 24 h. This included, fill (40 min), react (22.5 h), settle (30 min), decant (40 min), and idle (10 min) phases. Acclimatisation and granule cultivation was attempted *via* two strategies. Strategy-I (lasting 40 days), involved feeding 100% SWW whereas strategy-II involved gradual acclimatisation using supplementation of sodium acetate. In both the approaches, the total COD in the influent was kept constant at 225.8 mg/L. In strategy-II, the recalcitrant COD concentration initially accounted for 10%, with sodium acetate contributing 90%. Over time, the proportion of COD from sodium acetate was gradually reduced from 90% to 0%, while the COD from recalcitrant organics increased from 10% to 100%, keeping the total COD constant at 225.8 mg/L. Since the SWW contained organic-N sources, as the proportion of SWW increased from 10% to 100%, the total nitrogen (TN) in the influent rose from 20 mg/L to 30 mg/L, while the inorganic-N levels (ammonium-N and nitrate-N) remained constant throughout.

Analytical methods, microscopic observation of sludge and nitrifiers detection

Samples were collected from the SBR every 24 h and filtered with 0.45 μm nylon membrane filter. Ammonium-N, Nitrite-N, Nitrate-N were measured as per methods described by Prashant et al. (2024). COD, MLSS, MLVSS and SVI were measured based on standard methods (APHA 2012). Scanning electron microscope (SEM) was used to study the morphology and surface structure of the sludge aggregates/granules as per methods described by Phatak (2018). Fluorescent in-situ hybridisation (FISH) analysis was carried out as per Phatak (2018).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Direct exposure to 100% SWW led to severe biomass washout and nitrification inhibition. COD removal efficiency remained poor (~60%) and no significant nitrogen removal was achieved (Figure 1). The high toxicity and complex composition of the SWW likely inhibited the sensitive nitrifiers and led to microbial washout, demonstrating the unsuitability of direct adaptation.

Figure 1 (a) Nitrogen removal profile and (b) COD removal profile (strategy-I)

Figure 2. (a) Nitrogen removal profile and (b) COD removal profile (strategy-II)

In contrast, gradual acclimatisation using sodium acetate facilitated AGS formation and significantly improved the SBR performance. At 10%–30% recalcitrant COD, influent TN was 20–22 mg/L and effluent TN was 11.2–13.7 mg/L, yielding TN removal efficiency of 30.7%–46.5%. As the fraction of recalcitrant COD increased to 40%–50%, influent TN rose to 23.5–24.7 mg/L and effluent TN to ~20 mg/L, with reduced TN removal efficiency (17.9%–19.3%). Despite incomplete TN removal, nitrification was observed to be complete at this stage (i.e., 50% influent SWW). Microscopic examination revealed transformation of the seeded floccular sludge (3–17 μm) into compact, spherical granules (50–300 μm) as acclimatisation progressed (Figure 3). Such self-aggregation highlighted the adaptive strength of the microbial community to increasing concentration of recalcitrant organics. Comparable AGS sizes (200–500 μm) have been reported in refinery wastewater (Bucci et al., 2022), but granulation under such a low organic loading rate (0.14 kg COD/ $\text{m}^3\cdot\text{day}$), as observed in this study, is rarely reported. At 100% SWW, with influent TN ~30 mg/L, complete nitrification was established, with effluent ammonium-N and nitrite-N < 1 mg/L. FISH confirmed the presence of active nitrifiers within the biomass, even under high recalcitrant organics (Figure 3). The persistence of sensitive nitrifiers under toxic conditions can be attributed to the protective microenvironment provided by the AGS. However, TN removal efficiency remained low (~8%) due to incomplete denitrification, likely constrained by absence of an anoxic zone, and unavailability of readily biodegradable carbon. Her and Huang (1995) reported that denitrification with recalcitrant organics demands more carbon than with simple substrates. Nevertheless, COD removal efficiency exceeded 95%, complete nitrification was sustained, excellent sludge settleability (SVI < 100 mL/g) was observed with MLSS stabilised in the range 1040–1314 mg/L. It may be possible to enhance denitrification by incorporating an anoxic react

phase or by adjusting the operating parameters (HRT, SRT, C/N ratios), which can be explored in future studies.

Figure 3. (a) MLSS, MLVSS and SVI (strategy-II) (b) SEM analysis of the sludge and (c) FISH analysis after 100% SWW acclimatisation (strategy- II)

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